

Table 1. Correlation coefficients among genetic diversity measures in maintainer (B) and restorer (R) lines of rice.^a

	Quantitative trait	SSR
Pedigree record	-0.061 (B) 0.216***(R)	0.092* (B) 0.033 (R)
Quantitative trait		0.025 (B) 0.047 (R)

^a*, ** indicate significance levels of $P \leq 5\%$ and 1% , respectively.

Table 2. Correlation between hybrid performance (F_1), midparent heterosis (H_{MP}), and different diversity measures of parental lines.^a

Basis for diversity	Plant height (cm)	Total plant weight (g)	Grain yield per plant (g)	100-grain weight (g)	Grain length (mm)	Grain width (mm)
SSR markers						
F_1	-0.03	-0.02	0.07	-0.04	-0.01	0.09
H_{MP}	0.30	-0.06	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.01
Pedigree record						
F_1	0.34*	0.19	-0.07	0.43**	0.43**	-0.26
H_{MP}	0.30	0.14	0.10	0.01	0.26	0.05
Quantitative traits						
F_1	0.40*	-0.03	-0.18	0.16	0.05	0.32
H_{MP}	0.12	0.38*	0.40*	0.42*	0.23	0.01

^a*, ** indicate significance levels of $P \leq 5\%$ and 1% , respectively.

References

- Autrique E, Nachi MN, Monneveux P, Tanksley SD, Sorrels ME. 1996. Genetic diversity in durum wheat based on RFLPs, morphological traits and coefficient of parentage. *Crop Sci.* 36:735–742.
- Nei M, Li W. 1979. Mathematical model for studying genetic variance in terms of restriction endonucleases. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 76:5269–5273.
- Shut JW, Qi X, Stam P. 1997. Association between relationship measures based on AFLP markers, pedigree data and morphological traits in barley. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 95:1161–1168.

Epistatic QTLs affecting hybrid breakdown in recombinant inbred populations derived from indica-japonica crosses

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Inbreeding depression (ID), the depressive effect on the expression of traits, arises primarily from increasing homozygosity in outcrossing species. Heterosis (H), the superiority of F_1 performance relative to parental performance, is associated with heterozygosity (Allard 1960, Filho 1999). In quantitative genetic theory, ID and H are due to nonadditive gene actions and are considered as two aspects of the same phenomenon (Mather and Jinks 1982). Recently, Li et al (1997) suggested that hybrid breakdown (HB) in rice is part of ID due largely to additive epistasis. In this study, we examined HB in a recombinant inbred (RI) population of rice and mapped main-effect and epistatic quantitative trait loci (QTLs) associated with grain yield and

biomass, which appeared to shed some light on the genetic basis of HB in rice.

A set of 254 F_{10} recombinant inbred lines (RILs) derived from a cross between Lemont (japonica) and Teqing (indica) was used. The parents and RILs were evaluated for grain yield (GY) and biomass (BY) per plant in a replicated trial conducted at CNRRI in 1996. Genotyping was conducted at Texas A&M University, USA. A complete linkage map of 182 markers spanned 1,918.7 cM and covered 12 rice chromosomes with an average interval of 11.3 cM between markers (Li et al 1999). The values of HB (RILs – MP) for GY and BY were used as input data, where MP was the mid-parent value. A mixed linear model was used for mapping epistatic QTLs using

QTLMAPPER v. 1.0 based on a threshold of $LOD > 2.5$ (Wang et al 1999).

The mean HB of the RILs was -2.7 t ha⁻¹ (-54.6%) and -3.7 t ha⁻¹ (-37.7%), ranging from -4.5 t ha⁻¹ (-90.8%) to 2.5 t ha⁻¹ (50.8%) for GY and from -7.6 t ha⁻¹ (-78.4%) to 4.1 t ha⁻¹ (42.2%) for BY.

The segregation of the RILs for BY and GY could be largely explained by four main-effect QTLs and seven pairs of epistatic loci (see table). Four main-effect QTLs affecting both GY and BY were mapped to chromosomes 2, 3, and 9, which unlikely contributed to HB since the effects of two alleles at each QTL tend to cancel each other. On the other hand, all but one pair of the epistatic QTLs had significant positive epistatic effects on GY

and/or BY. According to Mather and Jinks (1982), this indicated that most interactions between alleles from the same parents generally resulted in increased GY and/or BY, whereas those between alleles from different parents resulted in reduced GY and BY. These results indicated that disharmonic interactions between the japonica (Lemont) alleles and the indica (Teqing) alleles at these epistatic loci were largely responsible for HB observed in the RI population.

References

- Allard RW. 1960. Inbreeding depression and heterosis. In: Principles of plant breeding. New York: John Wiley & Sons. p 213–223.
- Filho JBM. 1999. Inbreeding depression and heterosis. In: Coors JG, Pandey S, editors. Genetics and exploitation of heterosis in crops. Madison, Wisconsin (USA): American Society of Agronomy and Crop Science Society of America. p 69–80.
- Li ZK, Luo LJ, Mei HW, Paterson AH, Zhao XH. 1999. A “defeated” rice resistance gene acts as a QTL against a virulent strain of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*. Mol. Gen. Genet. 261:58–63.
- Li ZK, Pinson SRM, Paterson AH, Park WD, Stansel JW. 1997. Genetics of hybrid sterility and hybrid breakdown in an inter-subspecific rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) population. Genetics 145:1139–1148.
- Mather K, Jinks JL. 1982. Biometrical genetics. London: Chapman and Hall.
- Wang DL, Zhu J, Li ZK, Paterson AH. 1999. Mapping QTLs with epistatic effects and QTL × environment interactions by mixed model approaches. Theor. Appl. Genet. (in press)

Main-effect QTLs and digenic epistatic loci affecting hybrid breakdown of biomass (BY, in t ha⁻¹) and grain yield (GY, in t ha⁻¹) in the Lemont/Teqing RILs of rice.

Trait	Chromosome	Marker interval <i>i</i>	Chromosome	Marker interval <i>i</i>	LOD	a_i^a	a_j	a_{ij}
BY	2	C624x–G45			2.65	1.08***		
GY					2.26	0.55***		
BY	3	C515–RG348			9.81	-1.86***		
GY					8.37	-0.84***		
BY	3	G249–RG418			5.50	-1.54***		
GY					5.87	-0.82***		
BY	9	RG451–RZ404			3.53	-1.03***		
GY					2.29	-0.43***		
BY	5	g11–Y1049	11	L457b–G2132b	3.80	-	-	0.76***
GY					4.66	-	-	0.44***
BY	1	R210–RZ382	5	RG556–g11	2.58	-	-	0.42**
GY					3.98	-0.29*	-	0.31***
BY	7	G20–RG30	12	G402–RG20q	5.10	-0.73**	-	0.65***
GY					2.52	-0.29*	-	0.23**
BY	8	CSU754–G104	10	CDO98–RG752	2.86	-	-0.56*	0.52***
GY					3.95	-	-0.42**	0.28***
BY	2	RG654–RG256	9	CDO82–CDO226b	4.24	-	-0.68**	0.51***
GY					2.66	-	-	0.23**
BY	1	RZ382–RG532	11	RG1109–RZ537b	2.50	-0.57*	-	-0.54**

^a a_i and a_j were the main effects of the epistatic loci associated with the Lemont allele, and a_{ij} was the epistatic effect between loci *i* and *j*. *, **, *** represent the significance levels of *P* < 0.05, 0.001, and 0.0001, respectively.

Molecular mapping of quantitative trait loci (QTLs) associated with whitebacked planthopper in rice

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The whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) (Homoptera: Delphacidae), has emerged as a major pest of rice in India and other Asian countries. Classical genetic analysis of selected rice accessions resulted in the

identification of five major genes: *Wbpb 1* (Sidhu et al 1979), *Wbpb 2* (Angeles et al 1981), *Wbpb 3* and *Wbpb 4* (Hernandez and Khush 1985), and *Wbpb 5* (Wu and Khush 1985). These genes have been incorporated into improved germplasm to

broaden the genetic base for resistance to WBPH. The need to identify gene loci conferring durable resistance to insect pests, however, led to the molecular marker-based QTL (MQTL) analysis involving 96 doubled-haploid lines derived from IR64/Azucena.